

THE TSS - 1-R, THE NASA SPACE FLIGHT TETHERED SATELLITE - THE ODESSEY OF THE TETHER FABRICATION, FLIGHT AND POST-MORTEM

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Keywords : aerospace applications, composite structures, Kevlar, Electromechanical Composite.

The first plan called for a 100 km mechanical tether of 600 lb BS, to be used in a NASA Space Satellite project, but a year later a critical and complex 26 km electrical conductor cable was ordered. Producing a 100 km braided Kevlar tether, was unique only in proving that the every inch had the minimum required break strength. A quality control procedure had been developed previously for high altitude balloon tethers of 30 km length. Three conducting tethers were subsequently built for NASA, one of which flew on the 22nd of February, 1996. They were of a unique design, in that they did not expand or contract with the extremes of outer space temperatures, as would a conventional continuous copper conductor.

The satellite at the end of the tether was deployed into orbit from the Space Shuttle STS-75 Endeavor, dipping 22 km back towards the earth at a 200 mile altitude, requiring over nine hours to be paid out. It was intended to orbit the earth several times, measuring the Earth's magnetic fields, and then be retrieved - but suddenly the tether failed. The satellite, with its 22 km of tether, went off into space, and in a few days was destroyed on re-entry. This was the second attempt to deploy the tethered satellite, involving elaborate mechanical interactions precalculated by Prof. Colombo. The physicists in charge of the program were elated with the results of the second trial, and while not all the desired data had not been obtained, their had been great success and progress in better understanding and measuring Earth's magnetic fields. Though elated by the successful launching, surrounded by happy admiring Italians in the stands at Cocoa Beach, two days later they were planning mayhem.

The satellite had been built by Agenzia Spaziale Italiana in Turin, with the intention of retrieval and reuse, and they could never be consoled of their lose, of what was otherwise a successful mission. The tether manufacturer had now to face a NASA inquiry, with about one thousand feet of undeployed tether retrieved, and many hours of data on the voltages, currents, tensile loads, etc., plus the deployment system on board the shuttle. The history of the failure analysis, and the conclusions, were a prime study on the System and Materials, the quality controls, the management, and the relationship of Design to Deployment. The final report was the classic Camel - 'The Horse Designed by a Committee', with the tether absolved of blame, but this was an excellent case study of 'R&D on demand', and the role and fate of the Materials Engineer in a project directed by scientists.

Footnote: The proposition that a Cable is a Composite has been difficult to convey, since it is rarely viewed as a 'structure' - until an elevator or bridge or undersea cable fails. In both Outer Space and the UnderSea Inner Space, the Cortland Cable Co, has for 20 years supplied

synthetic fiber ropes and cables, ranging from the conventional copper electrical/steel or Kevlar, to the multiplex Fiber Optics/Spectra/Vectran, co-ax, etc., ranging from tiny strings to massive million pound break strength cables. These are complex composites - required to bend and coil.